

D4.6 – Impact Assessment and Exploitation Final Report

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D4.6 – Impact Assessment and Exploitation Final Report

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Abstract

This deliverable summarizes the exploitation, standardization and sustainability of the BIMprove project. Evaluation of the impact created by the project, outlining the exploitation model followed and sustainability strategy proposed. This includes key exploitable assets, contribution to SDOs, market readiness assessment and knowledge and protection management plan.

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Impact, exploitation, standardization and sustainability

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Acronyms and definitions

Acronym	Meaning
AECO	Architecture, Engineering, Construction, Operations
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AR	Augmented Reality
API	Application Programming Interface
BCF	BIM Collaboration Format
BLE	Bluetooth Low Energy
BMC	Business Model Canvas
CA	Consortium Agreement
CAD	Computer Aided Design
CC BY- SA	Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike
CEN	European Committee for Standardization
CWA	CEN Workgroup Agreement
DX.y	Deliverable x.y
EPC	European Patent Convention
EPO	European Patent Office
EU	European Union
FM	Facilities Management
GA	Grant Agreement
GUI	Graphical User Interface
H2020	Horizon 2020
IFC	Industry Foundation Classes
IP	Intellectual Property
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
JLM	Journey from Lab to Market
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
KER	Key Exploitable Results
KPI	Key Performance Indicator

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ML	Machine Learning
MRL	Market Readiness Level
MVP	Minimum Viable Product
MRL	Market Readiness Level
NDA	Non-Disclosure Agreement
OA	Open Access
R&D	Research and Development
SaaS	Software As A Service
SME	Small and Medium size Enterprises
SDO	Standard Defining Organizations (such as ISO)
TC	Technical Committee
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
Tx.y	Task x.y
UAV	Unmanned Air Vehicle
UGV	Unmanned Ground Vehicle
UxV	Unmanned Vehicle (x means ground or flying)
VR	Virtual Reality
WPx	Work Package x
XR	eXtended Reality (AR and/or VR)

BIMprove project

In the past 20 years, productivity in the European construction industry has increased by 1% annually only, which is at the lower end compared to other industrial sectors. Consequently, the sector has to step up its digitization efforts significantly, on the one hand to increase its competitiveness and on the other hand to get rid of its image as dirty, dangerous and physical demanding working environment. Construction industry clearly needs to progress beyond Building Information Modelling when it comes to digitizing their processes in such a way that all stakeholders involved in the construction process can be involved.

The true potential of comprehensive digitization in construction can only be exploited if the current status of the construction work is digitally integrated in a common workflow. A Digital Twin provides construction companies with real-time data on the development of their assets, devices and products during creation and also enables predictions on workforce, material and costs.

BIMprove facilitates such a comprehensive end-to-end digital thread using autonomous tracking systems to continuously identify deviations and update the Digital Twin accordingly. In addition, locations of construction site personnel are tracked anonymously, so that **BIMprove** system services are able to optimize the allocation of resources, the flow of people and the safety of the employees. Information will be easily accessible for all user groups by providing personalized interfaces, such as wearable devices for alerts or VR visualizations for site managers. **BIMprove** is a cloud-based service-oriented system that has a multi-layered structure and enables extensions to be added at any time.

The main goals of **BIMprove** are a significant reduction in costs, better use of resources and fewer accidents on construction sites. By providing a complete digital workflow, BIMprove will help to sustainably improve the productivity and image of the European construction industry.

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1. Introduction

Scope of the report

This deliverable evaluates the impact created by the project and outlines the exploitation pathways for the key exploitation results of the project, following this exploitation model developed for BIMprove.

Figure 1 Exploitation model and sustainability strategy of BIMprove's results

Approach and Methodology

This report is built upon multiple sources of information, including:

- Midpoint online workshop, 26 January 2022
- Stuttgart workshop (KERs were grouped) 27 Feb -1 Mar 2023
- Individual partner interviews in May-June 2023, the interview guide can be found in the Appendix.

Structure of the report

This report is organised as follows.

- Chapter 2 outlines all the 11 realised Key Exploitable Results (KERs) from the BIMprove project. A comparison is also made with the 8 Tentative KERs that were outlined in the Grant Agreement (GA).
- Chapter 3 outlines the aims of the formative evaluation and impact assessment of the project by returning to the 6 objectives of the project (according to GA). A summary of research outputs, conferences and workshops, partner interviews and videos is provided.
- Chapter 4 reports what has been achieved in BIMprove and how they contribute to the standards developing organizations, from Technical Committees to the IFC standard. The chapter also outlines the collaboration with sister projects on possible standardisation topics as well as the pre-standardisation activities with CEN/TC 442 that have been undertaken during the course of the project.
- Chapter 5 applies the methodology of market readiness assessment and provides a gauge on the potential of adoption of the BIMprove's 11 realised KERs - set at the level of MRL 4: Small Scale Stakeholder Campaign.
- Chapter 6 organises the partners of the consortium into industry, research, commercial and standardisation partners and elaborates on the exploitation plans per partner group based on the interviews conducted.
- Chapter 7 provides an overview of the intellectual property management plan making reference to the GA and the Consortium Agreement (CA) and the steps undertaken to protect the IP assets of the BIMprove project.

2. Key Exploitable Results (KERs)

A Key Exploitable Result is according to the Horizon Results Platform defined in this way: “A Key Exploitable Result (KER) is an identified main interesting result, which has been selected and prioritized due to its high potential to be ‘exploited’ – meaning to make use and derive benefits-downstream the value chain of a product, process or solution, or act as an important input to policy, further research or education.” In other words, KERs are the outcomes of the research project which have the highest potential to create value when the project ends.

During the proposal stage, 8 tentative KERs were specified. As the project gets developed, 11 have been prioritised because they represent the most important results from BIMprove, and are also the assets of the project that we expect to be able to exploit. Chapter 2.1 provides a quick overview of the realised KERs at the end of the project vs. the tentative KERs that were envisaged when developing the proposal. Chapter 2.2 then dives into the description of each of the 11 KERs.

2.1. Realized vs. the tentative KERs from the Grant Agreement

The table below illustrates how the 11 realized KERs, along with other content developed in BIMprove, map into the 8 tentative KERs specified in the Grant Agreement (pp. 34-35). While the structure of the realized KERs differ from those from the tentative KERs, the sum of the content is all present in the realized KERs.

Table 1 Overview of KERs

Tentative KER(s) from the Grant Agreement	Link to Realized KER(s)
BIMprove digital thread, cloud-based, layered service framework for AEC industries	This is the BIMprove system and is the sum of all the KERs working together (so in a sense KER 11 ; the BIMprove system as a whole)
Layer Services, developing / providing open software services for AEC industries	All software that has been created in BIMprove uses open standards for its output, with exceptions of some specialized microformats that are not standardized (but not proprietary)
Robot based automatic / semiautomatic building site tracking services for construction industries	This is supported together with the KERs for drones and robots (KER 4), BIM vs Point cloud comparison (KER 3), zone definitions (KER 10) and the main system (KER 11 including the Backend)

<p>BIMprove user notification and HMI services (BIM@Wearable, BIM@Truck,BIM@Anywhere, BIM@Manager etc).</p>	<p>This is supported by the KER for main system (KER 11 including the web GUI), VR (KER 8) and AR (KER 9) and also that BIMprove supports BLE tracking of devices</p>
<p>AR,VR representation services Of BIM and Digital Twin data for on-site and building office applications</p>	<p>This is clearly supported by KER 8 VR and KER 9 AR, but actually almost all KERs since they contribute to making it possible for content such as BIM-geometry and heatmap-pointclouds that can be inspected this way</p>
<p>BIMprove active on-site tracking services of machines and management and for repair and maintenance</p>	<p>This is supported since BIMprove includes a system for BLE tracking of devices, including a system where zone-based (KER 10) heatmapping of device count that is shown together with BIM and point cloud visualizations</p>
<p>BIMprove active on-site tracking services for construction-site safety service providers / municipal fire-brigades etc.</p>	<p>This is like the tentative KER above supported by the BLE powered device tracking system, showing zone positions (KER 10) with BIM/point cloud visualizations. It has not been tested with a fire brigade, but the underlying technology is made to support this</p>
<p>BIMprove Reference Architecture for AEC industries</p>	<p>This is supported with the sum of all the KERs, clearly showing that the innovative Digital Twin based system shows how information flow for better safety and efficiency can be created using open standards interactions</p>

2.2. List of the KERs from BIMprove

To present the 11 realised KERs, we present them according to the daily flow in the project. The reason these 11 was created inside BIMprove was that there was a very specific need for them in the projects, and there did not exist open and well-functioning solutions.

Below is first an explanation of the daily flow in the project. This is the flow we optimize for. It does not mean that BIMprove has to be used exactly with this frequency, it would function very well with more or less frequent cycles.

This repeating flow has as its basis the existing scheduled tasks that are linked with the BIM-objects. Each day, the BIM-operator looks at which tasks/objects should have been completed that day. Then the operator uses the web-GUI to request a set of scans from the UxV operators. The drone and robot operator uses their own technical mission planning tools to plan waypoints, scanpoints etc.

When the scan missions have been done, the BIM-aligned point clouds are sent back to the Backend. Now comparison between the as-planned (BIM) and as-scanned (point cloud) is automatically done. Image recognition from photos (including photos with position/pose information from photogrammetry) can also be used. The result is sent via BCF to the Decision Maker, who decides if construction has been done as scheduled and with an acceptable level of safety and quality. In this step, both AR and VR can be used in the consideration process.

If the answer is not clearly that all is acceptable (considering quality, progress and safety), the Decision Maker can ask for new scans, for manual inspection, to schedule re-work to complete the task, to schedule needed quality improvement in the built objects / safety mechanisms, or to ask for approval for a deviation and change the as-planned BIM. All of these steps and their results are stored in the Digital Twin for analysis and learning in and after the construction project.

2.2.1. KER 1: Defining scan requests using BIM and schedule

Leading partner: Catenda

Innovation: *Use BIM and schedule to request scanning missions (via BCF).*

It is required that the construction project has a detailed schedule for the activities that are planned, and a set of BIM-models that represent in detail what should be built. Each of the construction tasks are linked with the corresponding BIM-objects. The schedule, the BIM-models and the links between them have to be maintained throughout the construction project.

With this information the BIMprove responsible can plan which tasks should be checked each day. Due to the link between tasks and BIM-objects, the system can automatically propose which objects should be scanned. The web interface in BIMprove lets the BIMprove responsible create a scan request based on this using the open BCF format. The request contains who is responsible (person or team), when it should be carried out and the BIM-GUIDs of the objects that should be scanned. It can also contain a description with special requirements for the scan and typically also a screenshot visualizing the BIM-objects together with nearby other objects for context. Similar scan request can instead of asking for point clouds ask for photos for image recognition or for thermal photos.

This request is then sent to the operators for the flying drone and/or the robot. In the Figure below a scan request using BCF is shown in the Catenda Hub GUI, same can be done from the in-project created BIMprove user interface or other software supporting the open BCF API.

Figure 2 High level scan request

2.2.2. KER 2: UxV mission planning based on scan requests

Leading partner for UAV (flying autonomous robot) is ZHAW, leading partner for UGV (autonomous ground robot) is Robotnik.

The UxV operator receives the high level scan request described above. To do the technical mission planning, several practical considerations have to be made. The accessibility for the UxV has to be considered (can it safely reach and carry out the scan). Weather conditions like wind, rain or snow might create challenges. It also has to be considered if the scanning itself can negatively influence the construction process by distracting or being in the way of the workers, so scanning is often done after ordinary work-hours on the site.

Both ZHAW (flying drone) and Robotnik (robot) have created software for technical mission planning. They use the high-level scan request and the BIM-models as input when they plan start position, waypoints, scan positions/areas and final position (typically the charging station).

Both of these system provide user interfaces to create these technical mission plans, and then they are sent to the UxV control station that interacts with the UxVs to start the actual missions. When the scanning missions are done, the UxV operators upload the aligned point cloud to the Backend. When they upload these files they use a naming convention that will tell the Backend which high-level scan request these point clouds are responses to.

Figure 3 UaV control station software

Figure 4 UgV control station software

2.2.3. KER 3: Delta detection between BIM-objects and point clouds

Leading partner: SINTEF

Innovation: Component that provides better BIM vs reality capture, is easy to integrate and uses open standards.

The Backend has as a result of the previous step received a set of BIM-aligned point clouds from the UxV operators. Since we know which scan request the point cloud is response to, we know which BIM-objects were scan targets. PyBIMprove is the name of the software that compares the point cloud (“as scanned”) to the BIM-object (“as planned”). It first downsamples the point cloud based on a setting for performance. It can for instance group all points inside a cube with 1 centimetre size (a setting) into a representative point that has the average position of all points in that cube. Then it investigates one BIM-object at the time. First a minimal oriented bounding box that encapsulates the BIM-object + a tolerance (also a setting) is created. Points that are inside this box is labelled as potentially belonging to this object.

The next step is that the PyBIMprove software compares the observed points with the surface of the BIM-object. It tries to see if the fit is better if the points are rotated or moved, and if so it reports the optimal rotation/translation (see panel a below). Given that, it investigates how far the points are away from the surface of the BIM-object and creates a heatmap by colouring each point based on its distance from the closest surface of the object. If it is within tolerance (a setting) it is coloured green, if it is outside it is coloured red, and if it is inside it is coloured blue (see panel b below).

Based on the above, the Backend creates a BCF task that refers to the numbers about position and also the generated point clouds and the BIM-object that is being compared. That is assigned to the decision maker, who considers if the actually constructed object has the correct progress, quality, position and surface correctness. Based on this he can inside the BIMprove web application ask for a new scan, manual check, reschedule to take into account delays or to improve quality. One outcome might also be to conclude that the built object is not as planned, but it makes better sense all in all to ask for it to be accepted and changed in the as-built BIM because fixing it might be too expensive or time consuming.

Figure 5 Point cloud vs BIM: translation estimation

RT OpenD

— □ ×

Figure 6 Heatmap showing shape-difference between point cloud and BIM

2.2.4. KER 4: Drone / robot mechatronics for UxV

Leading partner for UAV (flying autonomous robot) is ZHAW, leading partner for UGV (autonomous ground robot) is Robotnik.

Novel features: The drone systems in BIMprove are created to fulfil the needs in the project. They support indoor and outdoor flights with on-board sensors, gimbal camera for data capture, and the process of scanning at fixed distance and angle to wall. It has a stable flight, flexible system, and extendable with other sensors/needs.

The ground robotic vehicle can be triggered in order to autonomously record a dataset. It is a data capturing autonomous mobile robot: The rover can navigate autonomously within a known map. In addition there has been created an extendable mission planning tool. The robot HMI is able to schedule the mission and command the needed actions in different points of interest without further user involvement. There is also a robot- sensor payload integration. The robot can trigger and offer data captured by mounted sensors, as well as provide different options from such sensors without the need of additional interfaces.

Figure 7 Panel A: The autonomous drone

Figure 8 Panel B: The autonomous robot

2.2.5. KER 5: Machine learning identification from photos of safety related BIM objects

Leading partner: VTT

Innovation: *New training dataset and new approach for ML in construction where it is using photogrammetry positioned photos for safety feature detection.*

This is called Risk Object Visual Analysis System, ROVAS. It analyses images captured from the risk zones and is capable of detecting the existence and placement of the required safety structures. Currently it is trained to analyse safety nets, barriers, and untidy places of images taken at construction sites. The result of the analysis is an image where the detected objects are marked with labelled bounding boxes and confidence level.

A dataset of 3500 labelled images has been used for training and validation.

This was used together with the photogrammetry positioned images. Here the BIM-aligned position and pose of the drone-camera was used together with this KER and the safety zone information that was added to the BIM model set (using KER 10). This way we could identify which of the photogeometry photos should include the modelled safety features, and create an alert using BCF if this was not detected.

Figure 9 Software for labelling areas in images

Figure 10 Result of running ML based image recognition on a construction photo

2.2.6. KER 6: Construction site Digital Twin serialization using open standards

Leading partners: Catenda and SINTEF

Innovation: *Export functions / serialization of files in open standards for the whole digital twin*

A key concept in BIMprove is to use open standards to store the diverse set of data that is being. Creating a digital twin of the construction process is a goal in itself, this is important during the project and for future analysis and learning. But most of the data is gathered while doing the day-to-day BIMprove activities to check for safety, progress and quality. This means that while the main point of scanning for a column when it should have been created is to check in order to potentially correct, the very much intended side effect is that the digital twin is continuously added to.

The digital twin consist of more that a set of labelled point clouds, it also consists of all revisions of the construction schedule, all revisions of the BIM models, all the positioned photos, and all the

discussions and decisions that is done using BCF. All of these are in open and widely used standard formats.

There does not exist a standard for how to browse the variety of data (Digital Twin) that a system like BIMprove creates in a construction project, but a lot of potential is there using the following two mechanisms:

a) Spatial and time based lookup. For instance, give me all point cloud data that was scanned in the first week of 2023 and that is located in the second floor of a given building. The same can be done by asking for the most recent version of the time of all BIM-models that had objects in the position. One could ask for all tasks in the schedule that took place in that time and place, or all BCF-discussions that had related objects there and then. Similarly, one can ask for all positioned photos that was looking at this location in that time.

b) Lookup based on BIM related information. It is possible to directly query the different BIM-models and their revisions for all instances of IfcWall on a specific floor, but also derived information like “give me all pointclouds that has been labelled as relating to any IfcWall on the same floor”. Or “all schedule tasks or BCF-discussions that relates to an IfcWindow”. Not necessarily using a text prompt, a set of filters would be simpler and work well.

BIMprove as it is today does support the data in open formats that makes all this possible, and is it possible to download all data in open formats. The browsing features described in (a) and (b) above does not exist, but data is structured to make it possible.

The pictures below show in panel a set of point clouds (though they look like one), each matching an IFC element. Panel b shows the sum of points that did not have any match in the BIM-models, in this case it includes material stacks, safety fences, garbage et cetera.

Figure 11 The set of all point clouds that was identified as belonging to an object in the BIM-model

Figure 12 The residual point cloud - all points that did not have any matching BIM-element.

2.2.7. KER 7: Open BIM revision based difference detection

Leading partner: SINTEF

Innovation: *Delta detection with BCF-support and with guid fingerprinting*

In BIMprove, when a new revision of a BIM-model is uploaded, a IFC comparison process is triggered.

The result is a internally a JSON file that describes all differences between the original and the new revision. It also created a coloured IFC-file illustrating the difference and a BCF issue list for each type of change.

The differences it can detect includes object that were added, removed, or got a change in properties or in geometry. It also attempts to identify if existing objects reappear with a new guid - this is done by fingerprinting the information. This is a challenge in real life since GUIDs frequently are changed without this being the intention, and leads to challenges since these GUIDs are the standard way of tracking information across revisions of the BIM-objects.

Tools that do similar things have stated to appear, but we needed a tool that was open and that we could include programmatically in BIMprove.

In the screenshot below a difference model is shown. The colouring indicates which type of change has happened to each object - for some there are several changes, and this can be filtered to give a clear list for instance only objects that have gotten changed geometry.

Figure 13 A difference model between two versions of an IFC architect model

2.2.8. KER 8: VR for the construction phase

Leading partner: Fraunhofer

Novel feature: A multi-user VR-viewer has been developed in the project. It can be used both with VR-glasses and on a PC screens, and simultaneously with some users on one type and other users on the other. It also supports pre-creating the assets that are used by the VR-viewer ahead of time (linked to the Backend) so that it can be much quicker to just jump in without a lot of setup and configuration.

It supports automatically loading 3D-geometry (including point cloud-data) and based on the available data give the user a selection of which data in a project he/she wants to interact with. A user can connect to a virtual room and join a multi-user-session. Possible actions include selecting 3D-models to show/hide them.

It also supports creating or reading topics from BCF, meaning that a team of users can discuss construction related topics in VR+PC. This has been shown to identify potential problems that might not come up with a less immersive and focused discussion.

It also has support for remote real time communication, meaning that teams at different locations can discuss as if all of them were in the same location on site and discuss current and planned activities.

Figure 14 BIMprove VR system being demonstrated on the construction office in the VIAS Madrid project

2.2.9. KER 9: AR for the construction site

Leading partner: VTT

Innovation: *AR-solution integrated into a safety and efficiency monitoring system*

BIMprove provides an AR application that can be run on an Android tablet or on the Microsoft HoloLens 2. This application superimposes 3D Building Information Models (BIM) of the construction project onto the image of reality and offers several interaction options.

In this application a user can investigate planned construction activities at the actual position on site. For instance, a HVAC engineer can investigate if the necessary openings for the ducts and pipes are all present and if there are any challenges that would influence the installation of the planned systems.

An important point for the efficient use of AR is correct and precise positioning in the relevant coordinate system. For this purpose the BIMprove initiated ongoing CEN workgroup for construction site markers is promising and important.

Figure 15 AR in use, with Hololens 2 and AR positioning marker shown.

Figure 16 AR in use, with Hololens 2 and AR positioning marker shown.

2.2.10. KER 10: BIM lightweight / low ceremony safety model and zone definition

Leading partner: Catenda

Innovation: *Easy and quick to create very simple 3D-volumes without CAD-tools*

Typically, safety features like safety nets, safety fences, and unblockable exits are typically not modelled in the BIM-models. One reason is that there is a time and complexity threshold for modelling these objects in software like Revit or ArchiCAD, and those who are responsible for this topic are often not used to using these tools.

With the software created in BIMprove, simple 3D objects (IfcSpatialZones) can be created based on a simple from a simple JSON file. The idea is not that this JSON should be created manually from an end-user, but that it is created by drawing features on top of a 2D-floorplan of each floor, and

then piped into the JSON-to-IFC converter. The result is an IFC safety model that validates 100% in IFC compliance test. This IFC model is then used in other parts of the BIMprove system, including checking if safety features are in position using image recognition.

Figure 17 IFC safety model created by the JSON-to-IFC tool

2.2.11. KER 11: The BIMprove system as a whole, including the supporting backend

Leading partner: SINTEF, ZHAW, Catenda for the Backend and the leaders for the KERs above for that functionality

Innovation: *A comprehensive system for tracing and documenting safety and efficiency on the construction site (and based almost fully on open standards).*

While the other KERs represent functionality that can be exploited separately, the system as a whole represents the totality of what BIMprove offers.

There are some existing systems in the market that offers some of the functionality of BIMprove. There are several model-servers, AR and VR offerings, robot and drone systems in the market. There are also systems that offers comparisons of BIM-models with point clouds, IFC difference detection and image recognition software. There are even existing systems that offers some Digital Twin functionality.

However, what is lacking and what BIMprove offers is a system that is designed from the start to improve the safety, efficiency and quality using advanced Digital Twin technology and as a bonus one that very deeply builds on open international standards.

Figure 18 Visualization of findings from BIMprove system as a whole

3. Evaluation of impact created by the project

This section describes BIMprove’s approach towards evaluation and impact assessment. BIMprove has connected people, technology and processes to move beyond building information modelling (BIM), improving efficiency and outcomes in building and construction planning and operations with digital twin technology. With this overarching mission, we developed a comprehensive end-to-end digital thread that can continuously identify deviations and update the digital twin accordingly. This way, construction companies are able to use real-time data to plan the fine-tuned allocation of resources, flow of people and safety of employees.

After 36 months of implementation, in this deliverable we present a methodology of how the project is evaluating its process and outcomes contributing to the achievement of the project main objectives. An integrated matrix of methods aligns the project objectives with specific evaluation questions, instruments for data gathering and impact indicators.

The presented approach towards evaluation and impact assessment is based on a set of actions carried out. Given the heterogeneity of collective awareness platforms (CAPs) projects, there is no single recipe for evaluation. In BIMprove we put a special emphasis on assessing the collaborative processes involved in the piloting activities and the expert view from the project team and the Advisory Board members. The analysis of this feedback has fed the impact assessment work of WP4.

Next to the overall evaluation and impact assessment strategy, this section includes a detailed description of the individual evaluation instruments together with a timeline to indicate the data collection phases. Potential risks and how these can be mitigated are likewise addressed. Following the guidelines of how to conduct responsible research and innovation (RRI), adherence to ethical guidelines that have been defined for the project in additional documents is obtained.

3.1. Aims of the formative evaluation and impact assessment

The main aim of evaluation and impact assessment is to ensure that the BIMprove system has successfully tested in real scenarios and can significantly reduce costs, allow better use of resources and reduce accidents in construction sites. With the evaluation task, we aim to prove that by providing a complete digital workflow, BIMprove is able to help to sustainably improve the productivity and image of the European construction industry.

A second aim is to provide evidence for the envisioned impact and present ways to demonstrate the project’s influence beyond the borders of the consortium. The project partners had an ambitious goal in terms of reaching out to a wide number of stakeholders. These ambitious project goals also set a challenge for evaluation and impact assessment, especially for the latter, as long-term impact can

only be measured after the official funding period has ended. In terms of evaluation, we thus have to distinguish between formative evaluation and impact assessment:

A. Formative evaluation: ensuring that the generated results and provided documentation of the BIMprove system are designed and implemented in a way as to satisfy the requirements and needs of the construction industry and the involved stakeholders. The formative evaluation assesses user-acceptance factors, like ease of use and perceived usefulness, to allow an iterative improvement of both the technologies and solutions.

B. Impact assessment: evaluating the results in relation to the general objectives set up by the project and validate BIMprove’s impact within the involved communities and its potential impact beyond, such as the EU Green Deal initiatives. The assessment provides insights into the benefits of our approach on an individual level as well as on the societal level of those communities involved.

The following list (Table 2) shows the main six objectives as defined in the work programme of the project together with some main implications for the evaluation of these objectives. It should be noted that while evaluation will consider all five objectives, the prioritization has been an important step in order to identify where the focus should be put.

Table 2 Objectives – evaluation

Objectives	Implication for evaluation
1. Develop a digital twin for building constructions, based on BIM	A digital twin, like in BIMprove, enhances the productivity, progress monitoring, quality assurance of the construction site, with connecting real-time data to the static BIM. While BIM is still used as a reference for the execution of the construction, additional comfort functions arise with the use of digital twins (scheduling, safety, analytics, etc.).
2. Automate progress and quality reporting of building constructions	BIM based building construction, gives the possibility to control progress in a digital way. The static BIM needs extension toward a digital twin (like in BIMprove) in order to establish the necessary services, which checks, updates or replaces the as-planned BIM with as-built information.

3. Improve worker safety	Worker's location can be monitored for safety purposes. This allows BIMprove and its digital twin to provide comfort functions to the workers, increasing overall safety of the workers.
4. Provide better control of building constructions	To increase efficiency, better management is needed, and workers need to have access to updated plans and progress reports. BIMprove allows instant access to information, schedules, location of equipment instantly.
5. Support standardization activities and industrial adoption of BIMprove	BIMprove recognizes standardisation as a potential instrument to transfer project findings directly into the market: standardisation activities will be fully integrated within the project. Open and transparent process of standardization will ensure that all relevant stakeholders can participate in project standardization activities leading to a higher acceptance by the market.
6. Apply digital twins in building constructions	BIMprove digital twin is designed and planned to be applicable in building constructions. The development cycles ensure the necessary iterations and adaptation to user requirements.

Each of these objectives can be evaluated with a range of indicators in different breadth and depth. In order to come up with a realistic and useful plan for evaluation, we need to analyse existing concepts and methods that related to these objectives and combine the most relevant aspects for our purposes. In the following, we briefly discuss current state-of-the-art of these approaches, concepts we can apply or adapt for our needs, and what it implies for the evaluation of the BIMprove objectives.

Objective 1: Develop a digital twin for building constructions, based on BIM

When a construction project that uses BIMprove is starting at the construction site, the initial BIM models and schedule have been added to the BIMprove Digital Twin. These are updated with newer versions during the project execution. Every day construction is done, scanning is carried out and the results are evaluated. Here AR/VR and image-recognition using AI can also be used. The results of these evaluations can lead to rework/rescheduling and/or changed BIM-models. Decisions are stored as the open format BCF, while point clouds and BIM are stored in open formats (e57/Las for point clouds, IFC for BIM). All of this adds to the digital twin.

The results here are supported by the KERs described above. The evaluation is that this process is supported by the BIMprove technologies and that the process is working. It has been demonstrated in a real life setting on the 3 pilot sites, and more than one time on all of them. A KPI here would be that it is tested 9 times (3 times for each of the 3 pilot sites).

Objective 2: Automate progress and quality reporting of building constructions

In BIMprove, the flow is centred around the Daily Decision process. Here the idea is that the up-to-date schedule describes construction that will be carried out today, and that after the construction is supposed to be completed, scanning by drone(s) and robot(s) are requested based on the linked information in the BIM-model (each construction task is linked with BIM-objects). AI-based image recognition can also be requested. When the scans are done, they are uploaded to the BIMprove Backend and analysed by the software (“pyBIMprove”). This pairwise comparison between scan and “plan” (the BIM-object that should be constructed) leads to an estimate of position/rotations correctness and also a new colouring of the pointcloud where the colour indicates distance from closest planned surface in the planned BIM-object. Each of these are presented to the decision maker, and this person then decides consequences in form of rework, reschedule, progress update and recalculations of costs. The BIMprove system presents the results including numbers and visualizations automatically to the decision maker, but this (human) makes the final decision about how to react to this.

The results here is that we have defined, supported and tested technologies and progresses that supports this objective. A KPI here is that drone scanning (best for outside/facades) scans 3500 m² per hour, while robot scanning (typically inside and many scans required to avoid scan shadows) typically gives us 700 m² per hour.

Objective 3: Improve worker safety

The BIMprove system helps with worker safety mainly in 3 ways.

- a) BIMprove allows for a much clearer discussion for the involved about what / where each of the construction tasks will be done seen in the BIM-model. This is also added to by visualizing the before-state via point-clouds. This means that the BIM-linked schedule can be used for a clearer discussion about the safety aspects of work that will be done. The multi-user interactive discussions that BIMprove allows in VR also supports identifying the best solution. Findings in these discussions can lead to adding important safety suggestions to the construction schedule via BCF topics. This is a basis for learning and evaluation during and after the project.
- b) BIMprove supports an innovative way of combining BIM safety models (including safety nets and safety fences), schedules referencing these safety objects (when should the safety objects be in place) and image analysis. The drones get a scan request and captures a set of photos. As

part of the functionalities of photogrammetry, the images used get annotated with their camera position and orientation. Using these and the position of the safety objects, we can check if all the images that should contain a particular safety object does so. This approach can also be used to check for the position of other objects, safety related and not.

c) BIMprove has support for BIM-related object tracking using a BLE (Bluetooth Low Energy) based system. This means that if workers or vehicles are equipped with tracking devices, they can be warned if they enter zones that should be avoided for safety reasons. The system supports real time visualization of worker/vehicle positions based on zones. This is done in the full BIM/point cloud based interactive 3D context. The zone based approach is chosen instead of exact visualization of single-device position to protect privacy.

The evaluation of the safety related features of BIMprove is that they work well. The greatest potential is probably its support of documenting and learning based on the Digital Twin.

Objective 4: Provide better control of building constructions

BIMprove enables discussions about up-to-date construction plans for the day and week in a context supported by BIM, point clouds, VR and AR. The links between the schedule and the BIM models supports documenting the outcomes of the discussions as part of the Digital Twin. This gives instant access to information instantly.

Objective 5: Support standardization activities and industrial adoption of BIMprove

As described in the standardization chapter in this report, a CEN working group was created to work on multi-purpose construction site markers. This is an important initiative since easily and precisely available human and machine-readable position indicator are of great value.

In addition, the BIMprove project has contacted buildingSMART International about possible improvements related to IFC-based schedules (making them more practical).

Objective 6: Apply digital twins in building constructions

BIMprove digital twin is designed and planned to be applicable in building constructions. The development cycles ensure the necessary iterations and adaptation to user requirements.

BIMprove has proved that the Digital Twin based workflow can be both practical to implement and give clear improvements for the safety and efficiency on constructions sites where it is used. In addition, it can give clear benefits for large construction companies that want to keep improving based on sets of completed construction projects where factors for success and failure can be used to create new best practices.

3.2. From Formative evaluation to impact assessment

As mentioned above, in our evaluation approach, we distinguish between formative evaluation and impact assessment (including the summative evaluation).

- During the formative evaluation, which starts with the very first project activities, experiences are gathered and reflected in the consortium in order to make sure the processes are optimized and we learn from our mistakes and improve continuously.
- During impact assessment, we aim to collect evidence for the impact that we are having on different levels mentioned above.

Figure 19 Formative evaluation to impact assessment

As depicted in Figure 19 above, there are different data sources for evaluation and different stakeholders. The main different data sources are analysed, and findings combined to get further insights.

3.3. Evaluation and impact instruments

In this section, we introduce the evaluation instruments that have been applied to collect data for our evaluation and impact assessment. Note: the content of this section is complemented by D.4.5 Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Final Report.

3.3.1. Research outputs

As part of BIMprove research outcomes, the project has published a total of 10 peer-reviewed scientific research publications in international journals or conferences. In this section we outline all of them.

Title	BIMprove’s White paper on basic concepts of data integration services for building industry using BIM and Digital Building Twins
Authors	Edvardsen, Dag; Ristin, Marko; Sziebig, Gabor; van de Venn, Hans Wernher
Year	2021
Open Access	White Paper on Digital Twins and Data Integration in the AECO Sector
<p>Abstract: This White Paper describes a proposal for a technology concept that will open the door to greater digitalisation within the construction sector, the core of which is a digital twin associated with a given building under construction. The proposal addresses the management of the highly heterogeneous environment inherent in the construction industry, and during the construction process in particular.</p>	

Title	XR Based GUI Concept for BIM Digital Twin Data Visualization
Authors	Kaj Helin; Vladimir Goriachev; Jaakko Karjalainen; Timo Kuula; Marja Liinasuo; Matthias Aust
Year	2021
Open Access	XR Based GUI Concept for BIM Digital Twin Data Visualization
<p>Abstract: This extended abstract introduces the eXtended Reality (XR) based graphical user interface (GUI) concept for the construction of Digital Twin Model. The abstract also describes Augmented Reality (AR) tool called BIM@Construction, which is part of GUI concepts and visualizes digital twin data on a construction site.</p>	

Title	Evaluation of BIMprove XR User Interfaces
Authors	Matthias Aust; Melissa Otto; Julius Schippert; Jörg Frohnmayer; Kaj Helin; Marja Liinasuo; Timo Kuula
Year	2022
Open Access	Evaluation of BIMprove XR User Interfaces
<p>Abstract: This work documents the evaluation of the XR user interfaces introduced in Aust et al. 2021 and Helin et al. 2021 in the BIMprove project (BIMprove, 2022). It describes the procedures followed in the different tests with their results and suggests a pragmatic and cheap way to estimate the readiness of a collaborative software system for a specific context of use.</p>	

Title	Storing, Maintaining & Updating the Digital Twin
Authors	Ruprecht Altenburger; Dag Fjeld Edvardsen
Year	2022
Open Access	Storing, Maintaining & Updating the Digital Twin
<p>Abstract: Digital Twin technologies are making their way onto the construction site. In BIMprove, automated data collection systems are developed, the data processed and fed to Digital Twin in a clearly defined process. Next steps are to test, adapted and optimize the developed functionalities on 3 pilot construction sites. Clearly, adjustments will be necessary in the transition from the laboratory environment to the very specific conditions on construction sites.</p>	

Title	BIM digital twin visualization in XR – Novel GUI concept
Authors	Kaj Helin; Vladimir Goriachev; Jaakko Karjalainen; Timo Kuula; Marja Liinasuo; Matthias Aust
Year	2022

Open Access	BIM digital twin visualization in XR – Novel GUI concept
<p>Abstract: This extended abstract introduces the novel graphical user interface (GUI) concept for the visualization of Digital Twin Model in eXtended Reality (XR). The first version of the GUI concept has been introduced earlier (Helin et al., 2021). Based on the user evaluation of the BIMprove XR systems, the novel GUI has been updated. The abstract also describes BIM@Categories, which includes six (6) different GUIs to access Digital Twin Model. Work has been done in a European Commission funded H2020 project called “BIMprove - Improving Building Information Modelling by Realtime Tracing of Construction Processes” (BIMprove, 2022).</p>	

Title	White Paper: Ontologies and Digital Building Twins (BIMprove contribution)
Authors	Mads H. Rasmussen; Pieter Pauwels; María Poveda-Villalón; Sanju Tiwari; Raúl García-Castro; Pierre Bourreau; Bruno Fies; Jonas Sschlenger; Bruno Daniotti; Seppo Törma; Mark Thomas; Michel Böhms; Gabor Sziebig; Angel Font; Eduard Loscos; Pablo Vicente-Legazpi; Peter Imbrechts
Year	2022
Open Access	Ontologies and Digital Building Twins (BIMprove contribution to the SPHERE whitepaper)
<p>Abstract: A review of existing ontologies in construction is presented (updated September 2022). Motivation, alignments and final applications with special interest on methodologies. Software Tools are presented in an Appendix. Some use cases are presented with different orientations. Final conclusions are oriented to new paths to follow in future developments, considering other technologies and commercial solutions nowadays. More than new ontologies the use of existing ontologies as DICon could help to standardize and make an ontologies map for construction possible. Progress with standards, as mentioned in a specific chapter about status of group CEN442 WG4, is essential to get a good level of interoperability, but it faces complex technical challenges. And the most sophisticated and perfect implementation sometimes means a non-practical approach, and too rigid to be used by the industry.</p>	

Title	BIM@SiteOffice: Comparing IFC and point clouds in Multiuser VR – Workflows and Tools
Authors	Jörg Frohnmayer; Frank Sulzmann; Matthias Aust; Jan-Filip Kvrjic; René Hellmuth; Cora Lenz
Year	2022
Open Access	BIM@SiteOffice: Comparing IFC and point clouds in Multiuser VR – Workflows and Tools
<p>Abstract: The BIMprove (BIMprove 2022) system's goal is to enable Digital Twins in the construction phase by addressing two main challenges. The first challenge is combining information from the physical object with building information modeling (BIM) models in a precise overlay of as planned data versus as built data. Doing this requires combining BIM planning information with as-built data collected during the construction and switching from a georeferenced position to a local position to visualize this information in the BIM. As-built data is obtained with laser scans from robots and photogrammetry from day-ahead planned drone flights and is stored as point clouds inside the BIMprove system's backend. To create a reliable overlay, BIMprove's partners have come up with a marker-based solution in which physical markers on site and virtual ones in the BIM model are automatically detected and aligned.</p>	

Title	Building's digital twin model shown as first-person and third-person views
Authors	M. Liinasuo; T. Kuula; V. Goriachev; K. Helin; M. Aust
Year	2022
Open Access	Building's digital twin model shown as first-person and third-person views
<p>Abstract: Construction industry is currently facing challenges such as a high number of occupational injuries and a somewhat weak connection between design and construction phases. One way to amend the situation is to increase data availability to construction professionals. Information about the structure and features of the building to be built should be shared so that various professionals can use the so-called digital twin model of the building for his/her purposes.</p>	

We have created a concept for delivering the building information model (BIM) that can be viewed in various ways from various devices. We tested the viewing and using of BIM in augmented reality (AR), with high-end eXtended Reality (XR) technology (Microsoft HoloLens 2) and a tablet. Briefly, according to our test results, AR seems to be good when user needs to be perceived him/herself as if inside the building model, and tablet suits for viewing the digital model from the outside of it. Novice users of the AR technology need much more support in using the technology than the experienced ones. All test participants found the concept good and the technology with which to use it as promising.

Title	Choosing between remote and face-to-face features in a test setting: methodology used in two usability and user experience case studies
Authors	Marja Liinasuo; Timo Kuula; Vladimir Goriachev; Kaj Helin
Year	2023
Open Access	Choosing between remote and face-to-face features in a test setting: methodology used in two usability and user experience case studies

Abstract: Remote test settings have become more common due to COVID-19. This paper presents two user tests focusing on the usability and user experience of an augmented reality-related solution. We describe the proceeding of the tests from the perspective of what has been conducted face-to-face and remotely. Thereafter, the appropriateness of the used test methodology is evaluated based on (i) the acquired results, (ii) the ease of using and understanding the methods and (iii) the test atmosphere. The physical presence of a person providing technical support to the test participant proved vital for augmented reality-related testing; the location of other test organisers appears more indifferent. Finally, we present the perspectives to contemplate when choosing between face-to-face and remote features in the test setting.

Title	Deep Learning Machine Vision Solutions for Monitoring Safety Structures to Supplement Building Information Models
Authors	Tommi Aihkisalo; Anu Purhonen; Ilkka Niskanen
Year	2023
Open Access	Deep Learning Machine Vision Solutions for Monitoring Safety Structures to Supplement Building Information Models
<p>Abstract: Building Information Models (BIM), provide a static view on building structures on design and construction time. During construction time, the safety structures and their positioning among conditions are vital for the safety of the employees on site. The models usually lack the temporospatial information regarding non-static safety structures as maintaining of such information manually is laborious. Thus, automated and continuous safety structure monitoring is costefficient and vital keeping the model up-to-date while improving construction site safety and risk information sharing among the construction related personnel during the project. This paper researches of providing up-to-date and supplementary safety structure information to building models by means of various deep learning-based machine vision solutions. The machine vision tasks consist of deep learning safety related object detection in images, point-clouds, and further instance segmentation to enable safety structure fitness determination by more traditional machine vision means.</p>	

3.3.2. Conferences and Workshops

During the project lifetime, BIMprove partners have participated in a total of 36 events, where they had the chance to share project objectives, activities and outcomes to a wide network of stakeholders, facilitating the impact generation.

Table 3 List of events

Event	Type	Date	Details
BIM FORUM 2020	Featured event	26/08/2020	Networking, Knowledge Transfer
IEA HPT IoT Annex meeting	Featured event	21/10/2020	Networking, Knowledge Transfer
The buildingSMART International Virtual Summit - 2020	Featured event	06/11/2020	Networking, Knowledge Transfer
BIM Speed Industry Day	Workshop /Webinar	18/11/2020	Networking / Workshop
BIM4Ren workshop	Workshop /Webinar	26/11/2020	Networking / Workshop
From BIM to Twin	Featured event	27/11/2020	Networking, Knowledge Transfer
BIM supports digitalization of standards for the Construction sector	Featured event	15/12/2020	Networking
BIMprove at EUROVR 2020 International Conference!	Featured event	15/12/2020	Networking, Knowledge Transfer

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Digital Twin for Cities: Initiatives from around the world	Featured event	15/02/2021	Networking, Knowledge Transfer
buildingSMART Norge faglig onsdag #12 (In Norwegian)	Featured event	10/03/2021	Networking, Knowledge Transfer
BIMprove project at BDTIC 2021	Featured event	17/03/2021	Networking /Webinar
BIMprove as part of the “Digital twins and integration of AI in construction industry” webinar	Featured event	27/05/2021	Networking /Webinar
BIMprove at Sustainable Places 2021	Featured event	15/07/2021	Networking /Webinar
BIMprove at CIB W78 - LDAC 2021	Workshop /Webinar	30/09/2021	Networking / Workshop
BIMprove at IEEE 29th International Requirements Engineering Conference!	Featured event	08/10/2021	Networking, Knowledge Transfer
BIMprove at Big Data Value Forum (EBDVF)	Featured event	11/10/2021	Networking, Knowledge Transfer
BIMprove at EUROXR 2021 International Conference!	Featured event	11/12/2021	Networking, Knowledge Transfer
BIMprove at EURAD-PREDIS webinar!	Workshop /Webinar	01/01/2022	Networking /Webinar
BIMprove at Big Data Value Forum!	Featured event	05/01/2022	Networking, Knowledge Transfer

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BIMprove at BDTIC 2022	Featured event	01/03/2022	Networking, Knowledge Transfer
World Building Congress 2022	Featured event	01/05/2022	Networking / Event
Sustainable Places: Workshop Ontologies in Digital Twin	Featured event	30/06/2022	Networking / Workshop
BIMprove at EuroXR Stuttgart 2022	Featured event	08/09/2022	Networking / Event
Digital Twin Lego Workshop at Construction City in Oslo	Workshop /Webinar	15/09/2022	Workshop
BIMprove at ECCE 2022	Featured event	22/09/2022	Networking / Event
CEN Workshop session 1	Workshop /Webinar	03/02/2023	Networking / Workshop
Sister projects workshop on exploitation	Workshop /Webinar	06/02/2023	Networking / Workshop
BIMprove at the Digital Real Estate Summit 2023 Bilder	Featured event	08/03/2023	Networking / Event
CEN Workshop session 2	Workshop /Webinar	22/03/2023	Networking / Workshop
BIMprove at BIM World Paris 2023	Featured event	06/04/2023	Networking / Event
BIMprove at BAU 2023	Featured event	20/04/2023	Networking / Event
BIMprove at BDTIC 2023	Featured event	03/05/2023	Networking / Event

CEN Workshop session 3	Workshop /Webinar	12/05/2023	Workshop
EU BIM 2023 Valencia	Featured event	17/05/2023	Networking / Event
Digital Twin in the Architecture, Engineering and Construction (AEC) industry. Workshop to Explore the potentials of Digital Twin	Featured event	05/06/2023	Networking / Event
CEN Workshop session 4	Workshop/Webinar	09/06/2023	Workshop

3.3.3. Partners Interviews (Self-assessment)

During the last project General Assembly that took place in Stuttgart between 27 February and 1 March 2023, AUSTRALO carried out a series of video interviews to key project partners in the frame of a designed campaign 'Impact Miniseries' to bring BIMprove's great results forward and get the attention from the general public that it deserves.

The campaign is meant to highlight the lessons learnt in the project, the ground-breaking technology that BIMprove has developed and the social impact that these innovations will create, from the project partners perspective.

A set of questions was proposed for the interviewed partners and they had to choose between 3-4 of them to reply during the video interview. The list of questions was the following:

- Tell us about yourself. Name, current position and role/function in BIMprove.
- Share something new you learnt from working in BIMprove.
- Briefly describe one ground-breaking or interesting technology or function developed by the project.
- How do you think the project results and technologies concretely will transform the European construction industry of tomorrow?
- What is an aspect that you would like to highlight of the project's social impact?
- What do you see in the horizon for BIMprove?
- BIMprove in one sentence.
- Could you share one experience lived in BIMprove that you will always remember?

In total, 7 partners volunteered to be interviewed and the result can be seen currently in two different channels:

A) Youtube Channel: AUSTRALO has created a new playlist gathering all the video interviews.

[Impact Interviews Playlist](#)

B) Project Website: AUSTRALO has designed a new section called 'Gallery' where all the video interviews are currently embedded.

[Gallery section](#)

3.3.4. Videos

During the project lifetime, we have generated the following videos (listed in Table 4).

Table 4 List of videos

Video
Augmented Reality (AR) visualisation of BIM Model
Multi-User Virtual Reality
Ground Robot BIMprove system integration and operation
Leica BLK 360 Point-clouds scans
Data-capturing drones
Detection of safety structures and untidy places in images
Mapping point clouds to IFC-elements
BIM@Vehicle: First Version of the UI
Schedule import and view
Revision change visualisation
PUC visit Madrid
BIMprove XR-Viewer: MulitiXR (Multi-User - Multi-Location - Multi-Device)
BIMprove Pilot Use Case Lausanne November 2022 summary video

<u>BIMprove 2022 wrap-up: a year of achievements</u>
<u>Women in BIMprove: Caroline Cheng</u>
<u>Women in BIMprove: Ingvild B. Småge</u>
<u>BIMprove Stuttgart Integration Meeting - March 2023</u>
<u>BIMprove presentation at the BIM World Paris 2023 by Wojciech Teclaw</u>
<u>Impact Interviews: Johannes Brozovsky, Researcher at SINTEF Community</u>
<u>H2020 - BIMprove: UI concept of BIM@Emergency</u>
<u>H2020 - BIMprove: BIM@Construction user test @Lausanne</u>
<u>Impact Interviews: Dag Fjeld Edvardsen, Co-founder of Catenda</u>
<u>Impact Interviews: Antonio López-Ríos, BIM Manager at HRS</u>
<u>Impact Interviews: Kaj Helin, Principal Scientist, Certified Project Manager IPMA Level C at VTT</u>
<u>Impact Interviews: Manuel Menéndez, Head of Civil Engineering R&D projects at VIAS y Construcciones</u>
<u>Impact Interviews: Gabor Sziebig: Senior Research Scientist at SINTEF Manufacturing</u>
<u>Impact Interviews: Miquel Cantero, R&D Project Manager at Robotnik</u>
<u>BIMprove in one sentence</u>
<u>BIMprove Final Review Meeting summary video</u>
<u>BIMprove CWA: Position Markers for Digital Applications on Construction Sites</u>
<u>BIMprove CWA: How the position markers work in detail?</u>

3.3.5. Call for Stakeholders Feedback

At the beginning of May 2023, BIMprove consortium launched a survey inviting relevant stakeholders, including construction industry organisations, digital twin tech providers, BIM experts,

other EU funded projects, digital transformation advocates and policy makers to provide their feedback on the BIMprove project. The survey was open for responses for one whole month.

Objective of the consultation

In 2020, BIMprove set out to revolutionise the European construction industry by addressing long-standing challenges such as decreasing productivity, worker safety, environmental impact, and budget misalignment. Today, BIMprove has developed a dynamic digital system that is designed to enhance productivity, reduce costs, and improve working conditions on construction sites. This solution leverages Building Information Modeling (BIM) systems and Digital Twin Technology, resulting in a more dynamic and multi-functional system that relies on real-time data.

Through the use of Artificial Intelligence, AR/VR, Unmanned Aerial and Ground Vehicles (UxVs), and wearable technology, BIMprove streamlines the digital transformation of the construction industry. With real-time information at their fingertips, construction sites can identify and predict early-stage errors, reduce costs, and minimise risks. Additionally, the system allows for better control of resources, reducing waste and ensuring a higher level of safety.

Over the past three years, we have tested our innovations in real-world scenarios, and shared our results with our stakeholder community. With this call for feedback, we aim to gather evidence and feedback from stakeholders to analyse the relevance of BIMprove's innovations and developments in the construction industry sector. We value the opinions of key players in the ecosystem and look forward to hearing their thoughts.

Result of the consultation

We have received seven replies to the survey coming from the following experts: BIM Technician, Research Group Director, Sustainability Manager, Managing Director, Senior Researcher and Innovation & Technology Advice.

Hereby we share the responses gathered:

1. *BIMprove technology has proven to allow construction sites to have real-time information available, allowing them to identify early-stage errors and being able to detect them, lowering costs of re-work and reducing risks*

Figure 20 Response from question 1

Comments:

What I have seen of BIMprove technologies at project waypoints, the proof-of-concept technology tests are providing real-time data and helping reduce errors and later-stage problems.

Following all the demonstrators there is a variety of solutions which address either getting real-time information, avoiding risks (I assume not only in early-stage but if a digital twin can be kept up-to-date then this might be ongoingly). Practically this shall result in cost optimization and better control of risks.

It is a new way to monitor and detect risks, also leading to more awareness for health and safety

2. BIMprove digital twin allows construction managers to control resources (people, material and machinery), minimising waste (time and resources) and to ensure a high level of safety.

Figure 21 Response from question 2

Comments:

I fully agree that BIMprove has made substantial steps towards enabling a real-time integration of construction management and scheduling. Though there is still space for significant future research to ensure full integration of data from the whole building-phase supply/value chain, though I would "fully agree" that BIMprove's contribution towards this future research & development is significant.

Well, any improvements in digitalization tools help. For better judge e.g. waste minimization I would need additional information. This is one of the key reasons why I selected "c".

The digital twin is not only serving relevant information but also raising awareness for health and safety.

3. BIMprove digital twin improves worker safety.

Figure 22 Response from question 3

Comments:

Construction remains a dangerous and deadly activity, any R&D that can improve construction safety is an improvement in this regard. BIMprove does fully contribute to improving worker safety.

From the demonstrators and pilot descriptions, I would say yes.

It is a new way of monitoring health and safety, including awareness raising and more constant perception of this issue.

4. BIMprove digital twin provides better quality control of building constructions.

Figure 23 Response from question 4

Comments:

While there must be more R&D across the building value chain that is focused on quality of built outcome, BIMprove does make a significant contribution to QC outcomes compared to traditional modes of construction. BIMprove lays significant and worthy ground work for this future quality-focused research work, demonstrating substantial impact.

It is an additional tool, but depending on the user friendliness and the acceptance of the (potential) users

5. *There is ongoing standardisation activity for unified markers on the construction sites for robots (drones and ground based) and scanners. Would you be interested to hear more about it?*

Figure 24 Response from question 5

6. *BIMprove is building an alliance who will be in charge of construction site certification for future proof construction sites.*

Figure 25 Response from question 6

7. How likely would you recommend BIMprove research outcomes and solutions to other stakeholders, on a scale from 0 to 5?

Figure 26 Response from question 7

8. Share your thoughts about the BIMprove project, if any.

Everything goes smoothly

This has been a fascinating project to follow from an advisory/external perspective. As noted, there is too-little construction focused research funded by government and industry is too-often execution-focused. There needs to be more R&D around Construction 4.0 / Digitalisation, and this R&D must be coordinated centrally in the face of such urgent challenges as global heating, carbon impacts of construction and building operations, and the resulting population displacement globally requiring new built solutions. BIMprove demonstrates how research collaboration can help drive forwards the construction industry into new proof-of-concept areas of progress and reveals valuable new areas for further collaborative work. The challenges that we face are global, and that is why international collaboration around building process-development is so badly needed. BIMprove has been a positive step forwards in this regard and I look forward to following the next steps in terms of commercial implementation and continued R&D.

<p>As coordinator of HE X project we are within the consortium at this moment internally discussing about how and with which topics approach you in BIMprove since there are few topics which are similar.</p>
<p>I highly recommend the research outcomes</p>
<p>Very good solution, taking into account the end users perspectives and social aspects. However, in the end it is important to increase the acceptance and use of the tool for the end users, stakeholders.</p>
<p>Basically, a good solution, which can give positive impulses in the discussion about sustainability and environmentally friendly use of resources in the construction sector.</p>

9. Do you have any recommendations to make to the BIMprove consortium?

<p>Not yet</p>
<p>I hope that this collaboration will live on in some form, and I would love to be further involved. Although situated in Australia, we can play a role in EU research through our developing network and the R&D work conducted in BIMprove would find significant value and impact in the Australian context as we look to building research in the Asia-Pacific context. Next phases must seek pathways for continued commercial testing and development, and this is an exciting scale-up opportunity and path for continued feedback and success metrics.</p>
<p>Not at this moment</p>
<p>The results of the project are excellent. It should be ensured that these are fully applied in the construction industry</p>
<p>A final Advisory Board meeting would have been appreciated</p>
<p>The implementation of the developed solutions in a "realistic" business model needs more attention.</p>
<p>Expand</p>

10. Does BIMprove represent a potential added value for your projects? Why?

We will see in the time

Yes, BIMprove can potentially add value to the work that my research group is conducting in Building 4.0 CRC. I would say that methodologies for 'live' construction project testing and integration of research are emerging and BIMprove reveals not just new technologies and tools for construction — but significantly a "way" of doing research that is valuable for construction improvement, that is conducted via live-tests as a means of prototype development. We are working on a number of similar test projects and this is why learning from the BIMprove team could potentially add value to our similarly aligned work.

Personally, I am pretty sure that there are some ideas where Horizon Europe project X can get inspiration or even continue. So, I clearly can see added value. From the point of view of a construction company each topic dealing with digital twins and providing new ideas and solutions is helpful, if this would be furthermore combined with standardization activities it is even additional added value.

As a representative of X, I have a network of 500 companies at my disposal. Wherever possible, I pass on the experience gained from the project and also like to network with the BIMprove project team.

The digital twin for construction perspective is interesting for the skills adjustment activities in other industry sectors as well.

We are not directly involved in projects.

11. Would you like to see a continuation of BIMprove?

Figure 27 Response from question 11

4. Contribution to Standard Development Organizations

The following section reports what has been achieved in BIMprove and contributed to the standards developing organizations with respect to the given suggestions in D4.1, section STANDARDIZATION PLAN which were updated in D.4.4, section 6. Standardization Plan.

The interaction with standardization committees is both very beneficial and challenging at the same time. The experts who work in technical committees are typically very knowledgeable which makes their time precious for both the standardization projects and their tasks in their companies or institutions. The technical committees (TCs) usually also know which standardization projects are important to them and which projects are to be started in the near future. The interaction with European research projects is in general beneficial for TCs, because it can bring new ideas, expertise and can path the way for new standards. However, one must be aware that standardization ideas from research projects are always in competition with the current priorities of the technical committees. Therefore, new standardization ideas must convince the experts in order to be included in standardization. Ideally, coordination with a TC takes place as early as the idea generation stage so that the technical input of the research projects either fits with the priorities of the committees or it can be worked on the question how to convince the TC's experts of the importance of the standardization idea.

4.1. Connection and interaction with Technical Committees

The project managers from DIN, who are participating in BIMprove established an observer status with the German committee NA 005-13 FBR "BIM - Building Information Modeling" in order to receive information about ongoing BIM activities on European (CEN/TC 442) and international (ISO/TC 59/SC 13) level. This includes information of the new working group WG 9 in CEN/TC 449 which explicitly deals with digital twins and BIM.

In addition, a Liaison of BIMprove with CEN/TC 442 "BIM" was successfully requested and established. This way, BIMprove representatives were able to participate at meetings of the CEN/TC 442 and the Working Group WG 9 with one expert for each group, to share documents within the project and to contribute to the work of the WG 9. The participation in WG 9 was explicitly interesting, as WG 9 was founded on an initiative of the Horizon project SPHERE and therefore open to the results of horizon projects about BIM digital twins.

Contact was also established with the German mirror committee of ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 41 Internet of things and digital twin who was collecting use cases for digital twins from many different fields for a future ISO standard. The technical coordinator of BIMprove was invited to introduce BIMprove and

its understanding of digital twins to the committee. Although BIMprove attracted general interest, unfortunately no use case could be submitted to ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 41.

The standards under development by the respective ISO and CEN TCs dealing with BIM were monitored, but no technical overlap with the current results of BIMprove was discovered. Therefore, BIMprove decided to do pre-standardization work to path the way for a new standard which could support the technologies, applied in BIMprove.

The project BIMprove and the project's standardization needs were presented to a German committee, coordinating the BIM standardization work. To BIMprove, as well as to the standards committee the most promising idea was to standardize digital readable markers for construction sites.

4.2. Proposed improvement of IFC standard

BIMprove has identified improvements in the IFC standard that would be needed to make it easier for planning software to handle IFC files. As the IFC standard is maintained buildingSMART, the buildingSMART member Catenda approached persons, responsible in buildingSMART with its suggestion for the improvement of the IFC standard. Unfortunately, Catenda has so far not gotten further with its attempts to further address the proposal within buildingSMART. Meanwhile the code in the Backend has been updated which allows BIMprove to use improved scheduling without the proposed change to IFC - it is using BCF instead.

4.3. Collaboration with sister projects

The sister projects ASHVIN, CBIM, BIM2TWIN, COGITO exchanged information about possible standardization topics and also other common activities on a regular basis. In addition, DIN was in regular discussion with Austrian Standards International, who are partners in ASHVIN.

BIMprove participated in a workshop about linked data and ontologies for BIM and Building Digital Twins on 14 October 2021, which was organized by Eduardo Loscos, who is leading the, Building Digital Twin Association, a spin-off of the SPHERE project. Eduardo Loscos is also chair of CEN/TC 442 WG 9 which was founded during the project runtime of BIMprove and its sister projects.

In connection with the planned standardization activities in BIMprove, the sister projects were asked for interested parties and additional participants could be gained for the activities. BIMprove participated in a creative standardization workshop of ASHVIN and also engaged in ASHVIN's standardization idea to hand in a standards proposal at CEN or ISO committees for the requirements of data acquisition of drones for a BIM digital twin.

4.4. Pre-standardization activities

Based on the considerations within BIMprove, the German committee and ASHVIN, BIMprove decided to apply for the creation of a CEN Workshop, a temporary committee, with the aim to create a CEN Workshop Agreement (CWA), a pre-standardization document which is created in a fast-track process and which form a first step towards a full standard.

The idea was to base the document on markers, developed in BIMprove. Those markers can be measured and used both by surveyors and drone or robot operators and also offer some functionality for AR/VR devices. They improve the alignment of point clouds with the BIM model and enable to detect deviations from the BIM model with high accuracy.

The application for the CEN Workshop was prepared within BIMprove and handed in to CEN in November 2022. In January 2023, the proposal was accepted and a call for participants was made on the CEN Website, the BIMprove website on LinkedIn by BIMprove and by DIN.

The BIMprove consortium participated actively in the elaboration of the document. In addition, it was possible to connect to experts who created ISO 19111 and to have a small exchange at the kick-off meeting of the CEN Workshop in February 2023. The small exchange also involved an expert from Leica who showed interest in the future draft of the proposed document. From a DIN standards committee an expert who is both drone operator and surveyor, could also be acquired as active contributor.

The document was created in 4 meetings, where the kick-off meeting was used to set the direction and the overall content. Subsequent meetings were used to discuss and revise the current contributions. A final draft was published in July 2023 and sent to the respective CEN/TCs, ISO TCs, to surveyor associations, and to other potentially interested stakeholders. The BIMprove partners set up a subpage of the BIMprove website which contained a video on how to use the markers, examples and ready to use QR codes which gave a real response. A link to this [page](#) was included in the mail to the Technical Committees and other stakeholders. BIMprove also published an article on its website and on LinkedIn, pointing to the aforementioned website. The LinkedIn article was reposted by the BIM representative of DIN. Three stakeholders handed in in sum 14 pages of comments (around 4500 words). This is a clear indicator of the value which is seen in the standard and that the experts see a fair chance of a wider application after entering the process of becoming a full standard in the future. The comments were discussed with 2 of the 3 stakeholders in a 5th meeting in August 2023. The CWA was revised and finalized around the project end. Once published, the aim is to use the final document as a standards proposal at ISO or CEN.

4.5. Standardization conclusions

BIM and digital twin are both highly relevant and significant topics. Basic standards for these topics are still very new, and standards based on them are still being developed. These are good conditions for European research projects such as BIMprove to contribute their findings and experiences to the standardization process. An example of the timeliness and potential impact of such projects on standardization is the establishment of the new CEN/TC 442 working group 9 focused on digital twins, which was initiated by a project under the Horizon program.

BIMprove found itself in a good environment to actively engage with CEN/TC 442 through a liaison and contribute to the development of emerging standards. After a coordination with the DIN standards committee for BIM, the sister projects and the responsible CEN/TCs, BIMprove was able to initiate and create a CEN Workshop Agreement (CWA). The standardization process led to an improvement of the developed markers and the resulting CWA can be used to underline the reliability and competence of BIMprove and its project partners. The partners aim to initiate a full standard which will lead to a wider application of the technologies applied in BIMprove and to a larger network of the BIMprove partners.

BIMprove also participated in the formulation of a standards proposal driven by ASHVIN. If this proposal is accepted and taken up by a TC, this will lead to common principles and requirements of building capturing by drones for the purpose of a digital twin.

The significant contribution made by BIMprove to standardization is largely attributable to the expertise and motivation of its project partners.

5. Market readiness assessment

This chapter applies the methodology of market readiness assessment and provides a gauge on the potential of adoption of BIMprove’s KERs. This serves as complementary input for maximising the exploitation of BIMprove’s results after the project ends and paves the way for transforming the project results into concrete benefits for society.

5.1. What is Market readiness? (link between MRL and TRL)

While TRL assesses the technology readiness of given solution or technology, market readiness provides an indication of the maturity of a given need in the market and offers a gauge on the potential of adoption of the solutions/ services. See Figure 28.

Figure 28 MRL – TRL

Market Readiness Level (MRL) is a scale that defines the readiness to go to market with useful, useable and used outputs (GA, section 2.2.3.2). These levels (from 0-9) are business-related situations that reflect the evolution of a project from initial software development to market leadership. As shown in Figure 28, from a business process angle, the MRL scale features four business process-oriented phases, from ideation to testing, then moving on to traction and finally scaling up towards a sustainable –and resilient– commercial operation.

5.2. BIMprove’s market readiness ambitions

As show in Figure X, the MRL scale is proportional to the TRL scale. The technological ambition of BIMprove is to extend the BIM process towards the Digital Building Twins, adding layer services, but where both the digital enablers and target stakeholders are in place, although not integrated. In other words, an initial offering is present, but it is not yet optimal. This is reflected with the objective to achieve a **‘TRL 6: Prototype System’**, which is considered a major transition from research and experiment to real life implementation and commercialization. This level calls for a critical decision-making on whether to make any further investment for a project, and if any, how to make the most out of it.

In terms of market readiness, we can estimate that BIMprove takes a baseline score of market readiness at **‘MRL 3: Needs validation’** as starting point. Taking into consideration the significant weight of the Pilot Use Cases on the work plan of the project, which will have a direct impact over the validation of the system, the status at the end of BIMprove is a score of **‘MRL 4: Small Scale Stakeholder Campaign’**. In terms of business process-oriented phases, this implies the ambition to leave the ‘Ideation’ phase and enter the ‘Testing’ phase, where usefulness is demonstrated among a limited group of testers within a “closed” beta scenario.

5.3. Importance of accelerating BIM adoption in SMEs in Europe

Within the European built environment, the 2030 objective is that all construction companies, including SMEs in Europe, adopt digital tools in a common and open framework to deliver smart-ready buildings and infrastructures. Insofar, digital tools have been increasingly adopted to develop specific and isolated tasks, but these tools have little impact in the processes of the organisation. A 2021 review of the use of digital technologies in the construction sector finds that there is a moderate level of BIM adoption in European countries, led mainly by large companies.

BIMs are regarded as front-runners to bring key enabling digital technologies and IT infrastructures together and overcome the high fragmentation of the value chain in building and infrastructure projects. In fact, the World Economic Forum described BIM as one of the 10 most promising technologies that can address the persistent fragmentation of the industry and the inadequate collaboration among the large network of contractors and subcontractors, mostly SMEs. Furthermore, BIMs can also contribute to lowering the barriers concerning insufficient knowledge transfer from project to project. The use of a digital model greatly facilitates the design, construction and operation processes in addition to providing an accurate and reliable multi-component information base for decision-making (see Figure 29).

Figure 29 The use of digital technologies in the construction sector, Source: EU report Digitalisation in the construction sector, April 2021.

The figure above lists a very interesting collection of emerging technologies related to the life cycle value chain in construction. It is interesting to note that the BIMprove project has developed and used functionalities and features related to all of the technologies above - with the exception of “3D Printing” and “Internet of Things”. The approach in BIMprove has been to develop as many relevant functionalities and features as possible, to try to reach the goals in the BIMprove project and to try to close the gaps in accelerating BIM adoption in SMEs.

5.4. Lean Business Model Canvas and Evaluating BIMprove’s market readiness

The Business Model Canvas (BMC) with its nine elements (Osterwalder & Pigneur, 2010¹) has been widely used to visualise the business model and rationale of how a firm creates, delivers and captures value. While very useful, the BMC is more suited to illustrate the business models of well-known companies like Apple, Nespresso or Gillette. In contrast, the Lean BMC is more suited to conditions of high uncertainty (Blank, 2013², see Figure 30). The Lean BMC also puts front and centre the problem and solution that are to be addressed by an innovation project such as BIMprove. It is also hypothesis-driven rather than implementation-driven.

¹ Osterwalder, A., & Pigneur, Y. (2010). Business model generation. John Wiley & Sons.

² Blank, Steve (2013). “Why the Lean Start-up Changes Everything.” Harvard Business Review, May 2013

Figure 30 Lean BMC

A lean canvas was also worked on focusing on KER 11 BIMprove system as a whole, including the supporting backend) (see Figure 31). The problems faced by customers and the BIMprove features and functionalities are made clear. The hypothesis is that the unique value propositions of BIMprove would further propel the features and functionalities to be ready for embarking on an early adopter campaign (i.e. MRL5).

Figure 31 Lean Business Model Canvas for BIMprove

The canvas shows that BIMprove has chosen to work with a clear and very relevant problem (safety, efficiency, quality). The core of the solution (a Digital Twin with daily decisions using scan vs plan)

has been proven to work and be relevant in testing. There is a unique value proposition. There is also an “unfair advantage”, meaning that it would be far from trivial to copy this (higher commercial value). The customer segments are BIM-oriented construction companies that want to be more competitive. The Channel to reach customers is to get a campaign to go from MRL4 to MRL5 and then higher MRLs. The cost structure (what needs financing) is mainly development, consultants, testers, cloud server and admin/sales/support). The revenue stream would be Software-as-a-Service (SaaS) revenue and consulting revenue, most likely going more and more for SaaS income as the customer base grows and ease-of-use increases further.

6. BIMprove Exploitation plans

6.1. Summary of the exploitation

The BIMprove project has created several results that will be exploited after the project itself has finished.

- All research, commercial, construction and standardization partners have identified KERs and avenues for exploitation (all have something, several many KERs and avenues)
- Commercial partners Catenda and Robotnik are using improvements through BIMprove in their offerings in the markets (Among other things point cloud visualization for Catenda and Robot control innovations for Robotnik. Other things are planned for the near future.
- Horizon Europe project “Humantech” (2022-2025) takes advantage of the Backend (aka “BIMxD” there)

Other paths are being discussed at the time of writing (August 2022):

- A spinoff is considered but requires a champion and financing. A strong pitch deck is being created with help from Horizon Results Booster and will be tested
- Another path actively being planned is the “BIMprove Alliance” - the purpose is to keep the network and results alive to create new commercial and research initiatives

6.2. Roles in the project ecosystem

The partners in BIMprove fill all the key roles in the ecosystem on the supply side.

The Industrial partners represent and are the type of organization that will typically use the BIMprove technology in real life. They are leading construction companies in Europe, being major players in their key markets (AF Group in Norway, HRS in Switzerland and VIAS in Spain).

The research partners contribute core competencies to take the BIMprove solution to be significantly ahead of existing solutions in the market. They are very important in contributing to better solutions for solving the problems described in the agile market canvas (safety, efficiency, quality).

The commercial partners play a different role than the research partners. A similarity is that they also work with advanced technology, but it is mostly driven by addressing the specific needs of existing customers and also to improve their product to be ahead of the competition. But though the deal with advanced technology, it is with a commercial perspective, meaning that it will be more customer oriented. Compared with the research partners, their day-to-day goal is to make technology that will be used by customers relatively soon, but when working in a Horizon 2020 project together with research and industry partners it is possible to work towards a more difficult, ambitious and long term

goal. This has worked very well in BIMprove, leading to advanced, useful and practical solutions to real-world problems.

6.3. Partner exploitation plan

6.3.1. Industry partners

The industry partners are AF Group from Norway, HRS from Switzerland and VIAS from Spain. They are contractors and property developers. They all found parts of the BIMprove system, including the system as a whole, worth exploiting. But there was also special interest for some individual parts of the system, especially KER 3 (comparing BIM and point clouds) and KER 7 (comparison of different BIM revisions).

The future role of the industry partners would be as users of BIMprove technology, not as software/hardware developers. That means that in order to use BIMprove in an improved production ready version, “someone” would have to complete the development and to offer/support some or all of the BIMprove technologies in the marketplace. This “someone” could be one or more of the other partners each supporting some of the technologies (KERs), or a spin-off from BIMprove that offers the totality of BIMprove technology or at least a substantial number of the KERs. As described above, a commercial pith process is underway and supported by the EU Horizon booster system.

In addition, the commercial partners will provide some of the functionality they have developed in BIMprove as part of their offerings in the market. This means that at least some workflows will be supported, as described in the subchapter about the commercial partners. A subset of the KERs would not give the full BIMprove experience, but some functionality could be achieved with simplified processes and workarounds. This is made easier due to the heavy use of open standards in the BIMprove components.

When the system as a whole is used by an industry partners, they would be able to change their existing processes to a small or large degree. The question is how much / how fast they are willing to change.

One example of gradual introduction is to use the system as a whole - but only do the daily decision process for the tasks that are seen as very cost/quality/safety sensitive - like the position and shape of supporting columns in the ground floor.

If the construction company was open for using BIMprove fully, it would be very BIM / schedule oriented in the day to day planning and dynamic adjustments. This would as an intended side-effect day by day create a digital twin that can have great value for conflict resolution and for learning.

When discussing what aspect that is most important in general in BIMprove the industry partners pointed at precision. Regarding the biggest improvement needed they indicated user interface and usability in general, and improved project overview and goal control more specifically.

6.3.2. Research partners

The research partners in BIMprove are Fraunhofer and University of Stuttgart from Germany, SINTEF from Norway, VTT, from Finland and ZHAW from Switzerland. Fraunhofer, SINTEF and VTT are independent research institutes while University of Stuttgart and ZHAW are Universities.

As a group their main outcome of a completed large research project is typically increased knowledge, scientific publications that provide publishing points, research tasks with financing of PhD students, and ideas and increased network for new research activities.

The research partners as a group indicated that most of the KERs are of interest for research. The only two exceptions to this are KER 1 (Scan request from BIM and schedule) and KER 7 (BIM revision tracking).

When it comes to how the research partners wanted to exploit the KERs they had a set of channels that would be used. The most important channels would be post-project scientific publications, getting new cooperation projects with private/public organizations, and having a better chance of getting new national and international research projects in the future.

6.3.3. Commercial partners

The commercial partners in BIMprove are Robotnik from Spain and Catenda from Norway. Robotnik designs, manufactures and markets mobile robots and mobile manipulators. Catenda make open BIM-oriented SaaS software for collaboration in the construction industry.

There was not a big overlap in which KERs the commercial partners wanted to exploit in the future. The only KER that was identified by both as being high priority was KER 3 (comparison between scan and BIM/schedule). At the same time both wanted to exploit several KERs, so the only KER none of them wanted to exploit was KER 9 (AR for the construction site).

For both of the commercial partners the BIMprove project has been very relevant. The idea of using autonomous devices to scan for BIM/schedule vs reality differences matches both very well. For one commercial partner there already exists a significant collaboration deal with a large hardware provider. This deal was a result of the work done in BIMprove. For the other a significant improvement in an already existing product was very important for its attractiveness in the marketplace.

Both companies indicate that the future increased revenue based on BIMprove technology is significant, even if it should end up with there being no new spinoff company created based on BIMprove.

6.3.4. Standardization and communication partners

DIN is the German well known standardization organization and member of ISO. Australo from Spain is a marketing agency with extensive experience with EU financed research projects. These partners are different when it comes to exploitation opportunities. One direct future exploitation is the initiative describes in the standardization chapter above, the one about construction site markers.

Other paths are being discussed:

- A spinoff can be considered, but requires a champion and financing. A strong pitch deck being done with help from Horizon results booster, will be tested in June.
- Another path is “BIMprove Alliance” - keep the network and results alive to create new initiatives

6.4. Joint exploitation plan

Below is a list of theoretically possible forms of joint exploitation (meaning done together by all partners or at least more than one).

a) License agreement with 3rd party: the organization(s) allows a third party to have access and utilize the IP for a certain time period in return for financial compensation (e.g. royalties on products sales or payment of a lump sum), under specific conditions and terms (exclusivity or non-exclusivity of the licensed technology, restriction to a particular purpose, like development or selling purposes, etc.). This instrument is usually used when the partner has not the necessary financial or technical capability to directly exploit the IP asset.

b) Transfer of ownership of the IP asset or assignment: the ownership of the IP asset is permanently transferred to an assignee in return for a payment of a lump sum, royalties, or a combination of both. The assignee acquires the full rights to dispose of it. It may also happen that the assignor is licensed back.

d) Spin-off Company, in the meaning of separate legal entities created to exploit IP assets, which are transferred or licensed to the spin-off company to commercialize them.

e) Joint Venture, in the general meaning of model of business association between two or more partners to undertake a common project or to achieve a certain goal. IP assets are usually brought by the partners for further R&D advancements, production, marketing and commercialization.

As of today, none of the alternatives above have been chosen. The door is not closed on (d) or (e), especially if a champion (one of the partners taking main responsibility) and financing could be identified. A pitch deck is under development and will be presented to potential investors.

What is planned as a “minimal alternative” is to create a “BIMprove alliance” in order to keep the network and results alive to create new initiatives.

6.5. Exploitation through Open Access data

A data repository with open Access data has been created. It resides on Bitbucket) and contains a lot of real world construction data, much of which has not been openly available before. This can have great value for the research and startup communities. The URL is: <https://bitbucket.org/sintef-manufacturing/openaccess/>

It contains a set of diverse data from the construction sites, mostly in open formats:

- Point clouds (e57 and las)
- Photos
- BIM models, both IFC and native CAD
- Schedules, both MS project and IFC-4D
- Photos, including labelled photos for AI-training

The license is Creative commons.

The screenshot shows the Bitbucket web interface for the repository 'SINTEF Manufacturing / BIMprove' with the path 'OpenAccess'. The repository is a Dataset named 'BIMprove'. The current branch is 'master'. The file list is as follows:

Name	Size	Last commit	Message
AFG		2023-03-09	Added structural models from the Fyrstikkbakken project in Oslo (AF Group in Norway)
HRS		2023-02-26	Initial data upload AFG, VIAS, HRS, ZHAW + image set
VIAS		2023-02-26	Initial data upload AFG, VIAS, HRS, ZHAW + image set
Zhaw		2023-02-26	Initial data upload AFG, VIAS, HRS, ZHAW + image set
construction_site_photos		2023-03-03	negative label index corrected on train_IMG_675.txt
.gitattributes	336 B	2023-02-25	LFS for files
.gitignore	624 B	2023-02-25	Initial commit
README.md	1.47 KB	2023-03-13	Added .txt and their purpose for construction site photos

Figure 32 Screenshot from BitBucket, showing the Open Access repository

7. Intellectual property management plan

7.1. Introduction

Based on the Grant Agreement and the Consortium Agreement this deliverable gives rules for handling sensitive and confidential information in the background and foreground knowledge. The document also provide guidelines on how the knowledge and IPR plan will be managed.

7.2. Legal framework, Background and Foreground

The IPR management plan in the BIMprove project complies with the rules defined in the Grant Agreement, the Consortium Agreement which was agreed on in the project, and the general rules and recommendations defined for projects in the H2020 programme.

7.2.1. Grant Agreement

The Grant Agreement is an agreement between the European Commission and the Consortium parties; the beneficiaries in the BIMprove project. Section 3 'Rights and obligations related to Background and results' define the rules for handling IPR, their use and dissemination. In specific cases the Grant Agreement allows the Consortium to agree on other rules.

Some basic definitions in the Grant Agreement:

Subsection 2, Article 24: '**Background**' means any data, know-how or information - whatever its form or nature (tangible or intangible), including any rights such as intellectual property rights - that:

- (a) is held by the beneficiaries before they acceded to the Agreement, and
- (b) is needed to implement the action or exploit the results.

Subsection 2, Article 25: '**Access rights**' means rights to use results or background under the terms and conditions laid down in this Agreement.

Subsection 2, Article 25: '**Fair and reasonable conditions**' means appropriate conditions, including possible financial terms or royalty-free conditions, taking into account the specific circumstances of the request for access, for example the actual or potential value of the results or background to which access is requested and/or the scope, duration or other characteristics of the exploitation envisaged.

Subsection 3, Article 25: '**Results**' means any (tangible or intangible) output of the action such as data, knowledge or information - whatever its form or nature, whether it can be protected or not - that is generated in the action, as well as any rights attached to it, including intellectual property rights.

The last part, results, is often referred to as "**Foreground**".

7.2.2. Consortium Agreement

The Consortium Parties entered into a Consortium Agreement before the project BIMprove started. The purpose was to specify the relationship among the Parties, the management and the rights and obligations of the Parties.

The Consortium Agreement in the BIMprove project contains rules and procedures regarding IPR:

- Ownership and joint ownership of Results. Results are generally owned by the Party that generates them.
- Transfer of results
- Obligations regarding dissemination
- Handling of access rights
- Non-disclosure of information
- Data protection

7.2.3. Rules and Recommendations for projects in H2020

The general rules and recommendations for IP management are given in the “[Your guide to IP in Horizon 2020](#)” by the European Commission. It covers IP management in the different phases of the project; Before Project start, Preparation and Implementation, and Project End.

7.2.4. Related documents

There are many other deliverables related to IPR management in the BIMprove project;

- BIMprove Grant Agreement
- BIMprove Consortium Agreement
- BIMprove D4.2 Exploitation and sustainability
- BIMprove D4.4 Impact Assessment and Exploitation Interim Report
- BIMprove D5.1 Project Handbook

7.2.5. Knowledge and IPR management plan

The Key Exploitable Results from the projects are described above in this text. In addition, the project has created other valuable forms of information/data. Through working together in the project there is also shared knowledge among the parties that should be protected.

Knowledge Management refers to the process of capturing, organizing, storing, and sharing knowledge within an organization to enhance its effectiveness and efficiency. The goal is to ensure that valuable knowledge and expertise are not lost or siloed within individual partners' minds but are made accessible to everyone who needs it in the project. During the project the strategy has been

very practical in that all text that is written is entered in a wiki (Confluence) and all partners have access to that. It has also been very actively used. There have been extensive general and topic-oriented meetings inside and between the work package partners. The work package leaders (and any other who wanted - many did) had bi-weekly meetings to synchronize about what was going on and about progress.

An Intellectual Property Protection Plan is a strategic approach adopted by organizations to safeguard their intellectual property assets. Intellectual property refers to intangible creations of the human mind, such as inventions, patents, trademarks, copyrights, and trade secrets. These assets are vital to an organizations competitiveness and can include proprietary technologies, branding, creative works, and unique business processes.

IPR through different main phases of the BIMprove project:

Figure 33 Intellectual Property Protection Plan overview

To protect the intellectual property assets of the BIMprove EU project, the following measures has be taken:

- Patents: Any novel inventions or processes developed during the project could be considered for patent protection. We have chosen not to apply for any patents.
- Trademarks: Any logos, slogans, or other distinctive marks used in connection with the BIMprove EU project could be registered as trademarks. We have chosen not to apply for any trademarks.
- Copyrights: All software code created during the project are copyrighted by those in the project who created it.
- Trade Secrets: Any confidential information related to the BIMprove EU project is protected as trade secrets. Confidentiality agreements will be used with all project partners, employees,

and contractors to ensure the protection of trade secrets. The basic version of this is covered already in the Consortium Agreement.

The IPR table for BIMprove is presented below:

Table 5 IPR table

Subject matter source	Assets and aspects in the BIMprove context	Patent	Copyright	Trade-mark	Confidential information
Software	ML based Image recognition, UxV control software, BIMprove Backend, etc		x		x
Scientific article	open Access peer-reviewed papers		x		
Design of a product	GUI of web app, etc.		x	(chosen not to do)	
Name of a product or service	Name of the commercial product stemming from BIMprove			(chosen not to do)	
Know-how	Daily decisions process				x
Website	BIMprove official website		x		
Open access data	BIMprove open access data repository		x		

8. Appendix 1: Interview guide for the project partners

A) Quick intro to this 1:1 meeting

B) Quick reminder about the KERs

C) Questions for all partners

1. Which of the 11 KERs in the project are most important for you (top, second best if any, etc).
2. Are there project results outside of the 11 KERs that are important for you regarding exploitation?
3. Of the results mentioned above, which specific aspects of each result are important for you
4. In your organization (especially if large) which part of it do you think would be most interested in the results/aspects? (maybe most relevant for large organizations)
5. From your perspective..
 - A, how ready for exploitation are each of the results?
 - B, how much improvement and/or change would they need to be easier to exploit And in which way?
6. How unique is each of the results you are interested in? What are the closest existing/available things that provides similar results?
7. Do you think that any of the results are ready for market exploitation?
8. Is it possible to estimate willingness-to-pay for this result in a commercial market?
 - a. How to estimate?
 - b. Is there something that can be improved to significantly increase the willingness to pay?

D) Questions specific to construction companies

1. In which part of the construction process / value chain are the KERs in the project relevant? Idea, overall design, permit, detail design, construction, handover, FM, demolition / major rebuild
2. How big is the willingness in the market to pay for
 - A, Safety
 - B, Quality
 - C, FM handover detail / Digital Twin
 - D, Efficiency

3. .. and will this change in the next 5 years?

4. Which products in the market (if any) provides features similar to the KERs in BIMprove? What would it take, if anything, to be better?

F. Questions specific for research organizations (SINTEF, VTT, ZHAW, Fraunhofer)

1. Has the work / results in BIMprove lead to new opportunities or projects for your organization?

2. Which KER topics do you want to focus future research on?

3. Which KER related topics do you think are becoming more important in the next 3 years? And less important?

4. Will you have PhD students working on these topics now or in the future?

G. Questions specific for commercial companies (Robotnik, Catenda)

1. What segments of the commercial markets are the KERs relevant for?

2. Which KERs do you want to exploit commercially? Prioritized sequence of those relevant.

3. For each of the KERs that you want to exploit, what are the

A, Value for the end user?

B, Willingness to pay?

C, Existing solutions that we will compete with?

D, How are we better / worse than existing solutions (if any)?

4. What would it take to make the KERs significantly more attractive in the market?

5. Are there relevant topics for Exploitation / Sustainability that are not covered in the above - in general or for your organization? If so, what?

6. Is your organization interested in participating further and in what way?

7. Is there any missing type of partner relevant to fulfill the exploitation mission?

H. Based on the above, let us quickly fill in the Lean Business Canvas (if time permits, if not done later)